

Code review is a widely used technique to support software quality. It is a manual activity, often subject to repetitive and tedious tasks that increase the mental load of reviewers and compromise their effectiveness. The developer-centered nature of code review can represent a bottleneck that does not scale in large systems with the consequence of compromising firms' profits. This challenge has led to an entire line of research on code review improvement.

Luca Pascarella

Augmented Fine-Grained Defect Prediction for Code Review